

COMPUTER AIDED DIAGNOSIS OF HUMAN FOOT'S BONES

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ABSTRACT

Segmentation in Computerized Tomography (CT) images of human extremities particularly for a tissue of interest is a difficult task in medical image processing. Human operator interventions require at times when an automatic segmentation method fails and gives incorrect results. This is often true in medical image processing where segmentation is difficult due to the restrictions imposed by image acquisition, pathology and biological tissue variations.

Initially the CT scanning of a normal male adult volunteer foot done and acquisition of CT scan data set completed and a manual procedure for segmenting bone tissues was adopted. The segmentation carried out slice-by-slice on 88 CT image slices in Materialise's Interactive Medical Image Control System (MIMICS) software. This finally gives a three dimensional (3D) representation of a human foot skeletal.

This specific skeletal 3D foot representation provides its prototype realization and helps in determining the shape and size of foot's bones along with joints geometries by observing relationships between different bones. The 3D representation of talus bone of foot provides an opportunity to view talus and analyze the ankle joint geometry that develops a favorable condition for diagnosis and treatment of a historical CTEV foot deformity also known as clubfoot.

This 3D foot representation also helps orthopaedic surgeons in preoperative surgical planning and consequently in carrying out biomechanics studies. It also provides a platform for finite element analysis.

KEYWORDS:

Computer aided diagnosis; CT scan; Modeling; Human foot; Segmentation

1. INTRODUCTION

The present paper offers a 3D representation of foot's bones of a live adult male subject from acquired CT scan data set of a subject.

The human foot is a very complex joint with many combinations of movements and motion [1, 2]. The integration of CT, medical imaging modality with computer-aided design to produce 3D model is an important area of development. Three-dimensional shape data of both internal and external human body structures (e.g. from CT, MRI, PET/SPECT, Ultrasound, etc.) are employed for 3D model development [3] and most recent anatomical models have been built for bony

structures from CT data. However, increasingly soft tissue structures also been built from MRI data. Surgical tool design, customized implant design, customized prosthesis production and customized orthosis production are other developing applications within the medical field [4].

Daniel et al reconstructed 3D model of human foot, restricted to cadaver left foot whose different bones were, kept in aligned position with the help of an acrylic frame [5]. Jacob and Patil also reconstructed 3D model of human foot based on conventional plain X-ray images. The geometry of foot's bones was rather approximate in their model [6]. Many new domains for real 3D modeling of anatomic sculpture require input images from variety of sources like photographs, sketches, computer made images from CT, MRI, Sonography and X-ray images etc.[7, 8]. 3D modeling of human anatomy is an open area of research and much works reported under this domain for different organ of the human body [9]. 3D model of human foot using CT/MRI etc is, reported in few engineering literatures. Some researchers did excellent works on modeling and study of human foot. From an extensive review of literature of ankle complex biomechanics, only nine papers have proposed mathematical model for the ankle complex [5, 6, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16], but their study was based on either cadaver foot data or on certain mathematic assumptions and in any case their study was not based directly on the live human foot. Udupa K. Jayaram and Hirsch B. E. did Kinematics analysis of 3D human foot's joint based on live subject's MRI scan data. This contributes the actual happening at tarsal joint [17, 18].

The objective of this paper is to develop a comprehensive approach for 3D representation of bones of foot of a live human subject by using CT scan imaging modality and understanding the important of this 3D representation from medical treatment point of view. The approach comprises of four main phases as shown in figure1.

In phase I, the subject was prepared for CT scanning and the foot's spiral scanning started. In phase II, the sequence of CT scan data of human foot is acquired from SIEMEN spiral CT machine, in Digital Imaging and Communication (DICOM) format; these acquired data are then processed in medical image processing MIMICS (Materialize Inc.) software in phase III, while in phase IV, the processed data were used to compute 3D foot's skeletal representation

The created 3D represented helps in diagnosis and treatment of common foot and ankle disorders [19, 20, 21]. The 3D talus tarsal bone geometry representation will found to be particular useful in correction of CTEV condition [22].

The presented work proposed a novel approach for 3D foot representation by integrating CT and medical image processing software. The approach provides a computer-aided tool in the form of 3D foot representation. The major outcome of this work is the 3D representation of talus that assists in diagnosis and better treatment of a historical CTEV foot deformity also known as clubfoot.

The paper begins with an introduction highlighting the area of work along with previous work reviewed on foot, our approach and outcome of the approach. The section two elaborate spiral CT data acquisition technique while section three describes our methodology of segmentation along

with end product of methodology. The section four present results and discussion followed by section five and six of conclusion and acknowledgment.

2. Data Acquisition System

(a) Patient preparation

A normal male adult volunteer's foot was prepared for the CT scan. All metallic material and clothing around the volunteer's foot removed as they can produce artifact and interfere with the clarity of the images. Since the scan technique was painless, the patient was not given any medication. The radiation dose given to volunteer kept minimum following dose optimization strategies during scan by optimizing tube current (mAs) and scanning length. These maintain image quality up to diagnostic standard [23].

The volunteer was then laid on the movable examination table of Somatom Esprit Siemens spiral CT machine at diagnostic center of India, in supine position with "Feet first" and "Toes straight up". An Acrylic support used to hold the foot comfortably and statically in this position. During the scan, the volunteer advised to minimize body movement by remaining as still and quiet as is possible for significant increasing the clarity of the CT-images.

(b) Scanning

The evolution from conventional to spiral CT has advantages for 3D volume rendering. With spiral CT, axial images reconstructed at intervals that improve the quality of 3D reconstruction [24]. After volunteer's foot preparation, his registration information entered at the Diagnostic Main Console (DMC). The scanned projection radiographs for localization, acquired and appropriate ranges for table locations according to length of the foot to be scan was defined. Image acquisition parameters then chosen from the available protocol menu of Somatom Esprit Siemens Spiral CT machine. A typical protocol for foot spiral CT is: "Extremities foot" mode was used [25]. Under this mode the scan parameters were: Scan time - 1s per 360° rotation, slice collimation - 2mm, slice thickness - 05 mm, table feed - 02 mm, tube current - 60 mA, tube voltage - 130 kV, 512 × 512 matrix and pixel spacing along X and Y are 0.5234375 mm used.

Scanning then started and 95 image slices, each of 5 mm thickness acquired. These 2-dimensional images of foot slices can be read into a 512×512×88 voxel 3-dimensional array. Here the number of images reduced from 95 to 88 slices due to the overlap information at ankle joint regions. Once the CT images archived to optical disk, they were transfers over an Ethernet network to a remote Diagnostic Satellite Console (DSC, from Siemens medical system, Inc.) for further processing and reconstruction. On the host system these image data sets were reviewed for quality assurance using Metal Artifact Reduction (MAR) and Volumetric Analysis Reconstruction (VAR) software and further reprocessed for CT image reconstruction [26]. These reconstructed CT image data set were saved and converted into DICOM format and were taken on a storage device from the local diagnostic center for further processing. For references, the four crude CT image slices of different cross section obtained from 88 CT image slices are shown below on figure 2.

Fig.2 Four CT images slices of human foot

3. CT image processing

In segmentation, a particular object, organ, or image characteristic is extracted from the image data for the purpose of visualization and measurement and it is a prerequisite for the majority of analysis methods, including image registration, shape analysis, motion detection, volume and area estimation [27]. In this case, the MIMICS software is used for visualization and segmentation of above acquired CT images data [28]. Here, the procedure for image segmentation is divided into following different classes:

- i) Data visualization
- ii) Threshold
- iii) Image editing
- iv) Region growing
- v) Boolean operations
- vi) 3D image calculation/generation.

Initially the obtained scan data of DICOM format were imported into MIMICS and converted into foot project file. In foot project file the orientation parameters (Anterior, Posterior, Left, Right, Top and Bottom) of sagittal, transverse and coronal plane are selected and all images are fixed with respect to these parameters. Also with “gray value interpolation algorithm”, the contrast of the entire 2D slice image data is also adjusted. The Threshold is the next action to be performed for creating the segmentation mask of different bones of foot. Due to the wide separation of gray scale levels between high signal intensity of bone and other soft tissues, we define bone based on a lower and a higher threshold value so that it can be easily segmented [29]. During threshold adjustment of different slices with different gray values it is observed that more soft tissue other than bones are appear in the mask if the selected gray value goes below 1350, in addition, the appeared bone was disappeared if selected gray value goes above 2300. Hence, the bone tissue of interest is defined as having 1350 lower and 2300 upper gray value threshold. The pixel value of the segmented object must be in between these threshold values. Therefore, the accentuating or deleting all pixels above or below these threshold values is sufficient to provide the required classification.

Fig.3 Threshold profile of bone tissue of human foot

Figure 3 represents the profile of the gray value having minimum of 900 and maximum of 2300 gray value units. The profile started from internal zone of tibia bone having gray value 1350 units that reach to a maximum value of 2300 at outer bone region and then start falling to 900 for soft tissue zone. After fixing these threshold value most of the bone tissue were fixed into mask and is shown in above profile, however some image editing operations like erasing, drawing and then the region of interest is isolated from the whole image by ‘region growing’ followed by ‘dynamic region growing’ tools. The region growing tool limits the region of interest and can help in separating parts while dynamic region growing allows to segment cracks in targeted small objects, where following segmentation rule is obeyed [28].

$$\left| \hat{i} - i \right| < \delta \quad \text{where}$$

\hat{i} = the average gray value

i = the new gray value

δ = the deviation.

According to this segmentation rule, a threshold value of the created mask would be set automatically. Hence, the new mask would begin when a pixel is selected in image and the MIMICS will start comparing the gray values of the neighboring pixel in image slice, in this way the pixels with gray values that obey the above rules would be added to the new mask and upper and lower threshold value were specified. The deviation means that the region will grow to a density values slightly above and below the selected pixel’s values. If the deviation is too big, it is possible to get all the soft tissues and in case, if it is too small it is not possible to get all the regions of interest. Hence, care must be taken while choosing the deviation value. As here the region of interest is bones, therefore we choose the pixels that lie in the threshold range of bone tissue. In this way after getting color masks of different bones the morphological operations like, closing, eroding, dilating etc. [30], were applied on these masks all these take or add pixels from source masks and help in getting the real shape. The Boolean operations (subtraction, union, intersection) allow to make all different kinds of combinations based on two masks created during region growing, this is useful to reduce the work that needs to be done when separating two bone joints. After performing appropriate Boolean operation on selected source masks, the threshold of resulting mask is automatically updated according to the values of selected masks. Figure 4 shows two segmented slices of right foot of subject from 88 such segmented slices.

Fig. 4 Region grow segmented image of two slices

Therefore, slice-by-slice segmentation of bone tissue based on threshold, followed by cleaning via mathematical morphological operations, different bones were segmented with region-growing and connected components observation. In this way, all the bone regions of interest are segmented and new masks in different color of different bones were created. All operations were performed with close supervision of a human operator. In this way a 3D representation of foot of high quality is computed and is shown in figure 5.

Fig. 5 Computer Aided diagnosis of bones of live human foot

In order to study congenital CTEV foot deformity i.e. deformity of talus [22] it is necessary to visualize the geometry of talus from CAD point of view, therefore the individual 3D view of the talus bone obtained from the above foot representation is shown in figure 6 below.

Fig. 6 Two views of bone of talus of human foot

4. Results and Discussion

Figure 5 shows the computerized three-dimensional representation of a human foot, reconstructed from the sequence of acquired CT images by the image processing methodology as described above. This representation can be rendered for showing outline of the foot and within these outlines; the anatomical structure of interest can be selected for visualization of actual geometry. This allows the visualization of a source in its context, and should aid in finding the correct structure in which the activity of interest takes place [31]. This representation of foot is anatomically plausible, accurate and true hence, it realistically approximates a human male foot that give more information of whole 3D foot shape with only one data set and this information helps in drawing the physical interpretations of foot features.

From this 3D representation, the total number of bones in the foot is found to be 24 having normal shape and size. The two lower bone of leg namely tibia and fibula meeting with talus, form the ankle joint and in that joint medial extension of tibia and lateral extension of fibula known as medial and lateral malleolus helps in holding the talus at appropriate place. The back part of the foot having heel bone is the largest bone in the foot, known as calcaneus and is connected to the talus. The set of five bones namely talus, calcaneus, cuboid, navicular, cuneiforms are interconnected together, and lying just below the ankle joint are called tarsal bones. Finally, there are bones of the toes and phalanges. The tarsal and metatarsal bones arranged themselves in the form of an arc and viewed clearly from its right side during rendering constituents longitudinal arch of foot [32]. Hence, the reconstructed 3D representation of figure 5 provides a familiar means of viewing foot anatomy and is useful for visualization, shape measurement and simulation. Such an anthropomorphic phantom has several interesting application in medical science.

The representation provide an opportunity to view the talus tarsal bone of the foot whose upper smooth surface articulate with lower surface of tibia, medial malleolus of tibia and lateral malleolus of fibula and form a very important load bearing joint known as ankle joint. This ankle joint is responsible for flexion and extension of foot. The lower surface of the talus that rests on and articulates with the calcaneus form the subtalar joints and is responsible for inversion and eversion motion of the foot. The anteriorly projected part of talus is known as talus head whose constricted upper part is called talus neck. The anterior surface of the head of the talus articulates with the navicular bone. The geometry of the talus gives us an impact to look interestingly into an important congenital foot deformity called congenital talipes equinovarus (CTEV). Hence, the abnormal geometrical details obtained from CTEV patient may be compare with the above geometry and a better correction idea can be develop to treat abnormal foot. The outcome of the methodology gives clear information to an orthopaedician about major orthopaedic abnormality in case if the foot is having and in that case, he is in a better position to judge the treatment

The developed method relies mostly on manual intervention to a large extent and need very careful morphological operation to correct the segmentation considering the complexity of joints and bone's structure of foot. This means that if one uses medical image processing software and if the images are processed with the methodology described above then by choosing threshold (depends on individual bones tissue properties from standard table if available) then an accurate and exact representation of foot can be achieved. It should be kept in mind that in case when standard values of threshold is used then by using the above method carefully, different users will get the same representation of a particular foot each time. The representation substitute variant situations for examples foot of male and female, child and adult, normal subject and patient. Thus the developed method will be useful for representation of foot under the situations when accuracy

in individual representation particularly analysis of complex foot joint is required. The technique will also be useful in diagnosis and treatment of the foot having arthritics problems.

This research proposes a novel computer assisted representation of foot by integrating CT and an image processing tools. The representation focus on new insights pertaining to the detailed look of talus bone based on patient-specific image data. This influences the medical community and the patient suffering from foot disorder. The approach provides a better understanding of normal and abnormal orthopaedic foot. The approach will provide the medical community with a computer aided tool to reduce the number of in-vivo test by better representation with the help of advance computation method. The successful implementation of this novel technique might result in reducing the number of foot disorder cases by improving medical diagnostic infrastructure. The methodology is distinct in the sense that it focused on human foot only. The generated 3D foot representation mainly depends on the quality, number, and position of input images of the subject. If the proper protocol during scanning is not chosen then the obtained CT images are poor in quality and better result cannot be guaranteed. The methodology of representation can be extended for more number of feet by taking their scan data

5. Conclusion

The research proposes a novel approach for computer assisted 3D foot representation by integrating CT medical imaging modality and medical image processing tool. The approach is discussed and implemented for better understanding of human foot. The approach will influence the medical community and related patient by providing a computer aided tool in the form of 3D foot representation. This reduces the no. of in-vivo test by improving medical diagnosis. The research bridges the gap between CT and clinical study for foot treatment by effective utilization of advance available imaging resources (CT and mimics).

The presented work contributes to the area of computer-aided surgery planning in particular for orthopaedic application and consequently in carrying out biomechanics studies. The major outcome of this representation is the details geometrical visualization of talus bone that assists in diagnosis and better treatment of a historical medical condition of foot known as CTEV (Congenital Talipes Equinovarus). Further downstream application of this representation is finite element analysis that will be helpful for future biomechanics research on human foot.

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